

Voice Prints

Para Alfredo Garcia y Florian Vlashi

Helena Palma

Vn solo

$\text{♩} = 60$

ancestral father

subharmonics

Detailed description: This block contains the first system of musical notation. It features a single staff for a violin solo in the treble clef. The tempo is marked as quarter note = 60. The key signature has two flats (B-flat and E-flat). The time signature starts in 4/4, changes to 3/4, and then returns to 4/4. The music consists of several measures of notes, some with circles above them, and a section labeled 'subharmonics' with a double bar line and a fermata-like symbol.

7

$\text{♩} = 80$

1: Preguntas

Bar solo

Dón- de? dón- de?

(Ubykh: 'dónde')

Voz

/ma: - k'j'a/

Detailed description: This block contains the second system of musical notation. It includes a baritone solo staff in the bass clef and a vocal staff in the soprano clef. The tempo is marked as quarter note = 80. A box labeled '1: Preguntas' is positioned above the baritone staff. The lyrics 'Dón- de? dón- de?' are written below the baritone staff, and '(Ubykh: 'dónde')' is written below the vocal staff. The phonetic transcription '/ma: - k'j'a/' is written below the vocal staff. The music includes various rhythmic values and accidentals.

11

Bar solo

dón- de? u - bi sunt?

SP

Detailed description: This block contains the third system of musical notation. It features a baritone solo staff in the bass clef and a violin staff in the treble clef. The lyrics 'dón- de? u - bi sunt?' are written below the baritone staff. The violin part includes a section marked 'SP' (Sforzando) with a dynamic hairpin. The time signature changes from 4/4 to 3/4 and back to 4/4.

15

(Ubykh: 'dónde están?')

Voz

/mə - xa- nay?/

ráfaga trm

Detailed description: This block contains the fourth system of musical notation. It includes a vocal staff in the soprano clef and a violin staff in the treble clef. The lyrics '(Ubykh: 'dónde están?')' are written above the vocal staff, and the phonetic transcription '/mə - xa- nay?/' is written below it. The violin part includes a section marked 'ráfaga trm' (ráfaga tremolando). The time signature changes from 4/4 to 3/4.

19 (Ubykh)
(Qué ha pasado?)

Voz

/sa-ʃ - q'áy?/

SP

ráfaga *agresivo* *ráfagas*

23 (¿Dónde están?)

Bar solo

U- bi sunt? Dón-de? On - són?

29 1: Antepasados ♩ = 60

Bar solo

E - bu - ria, hi-ja de Ka

34

Bar solo

lue - ni. A - pa - nus, hi-jo de Am - bo - li hi-jo de A -

43 *espíritu guerrero*

Bar solo

pi Breo - gan, son of Brath, son of Sru, son of Goi-del Glas

2: Canto - Recuerdos

49

Bar solo

a - u - o a
/a - o u - uo a

54

Bar solo

a
α/

(Griego) (Ubykh) (Alemán)

glos - sa /bhz/ spra - che

59

Bar solo

They are chained in an e - vent of in - fi - nite du -

(Albanés)

gju - hë

Canto - Recuerdos

63

Bar solo

ra - tion. a a
/a - u - o/

canto violin

67

Bar solo

Voz

sus vo - ces bra - man en el tiem - po

71

Bar solo

Voz

ruido del viento /h

76

Bar solo

Voz

hi i - y u o u/ ruido del viento /s

82 (fricativas del Ubykh) (Albanés: 'por qué?')

Voz

f - ɬ s ʃ ʃ s pse/

Bar solo

En mi me - mo - ria de la nie ve

92

1: Llamada - Evocación

Bar solo

Kroy - kha-sis Kroy - kha-sis laes-pi - ra - al
(Escita: 'Cáucaso')

96

Bar solo

del bra - mi - do del tiem - em - po

98

3 La duración

Bar solo

die - se Da - uer was war sie?

102

Bar solo

was - war sie war sie ein Ze - it - raum?

106

Bar solo

Et-was Mess - ba - res ei-ne Ge-wiss-heit?

die Da-uer was ei-n Ge fühl das

111

Bar solo

die Da-uer was ei-n Ge fühl das

Nein!

116

4 Sinera

Bar solo

Le - bens-ge - fühl

Le - bens-ge - fühl

121

Bar solo

a - a la ne-gra bar - ca

a - a la ne-gra bar - ca

126

Bar solo

por mi vi - gi - la a - a ve pel meu

130 *vibrato*

Bar solo

som - ni del mar de Si - ne - ra

134

5 Recuerdos

Bar solo

als meus ulls

137

Bar solo

ja no sa - ben sa - ben

140

Bar solo

si - nó con - tem - plar - r di - es i sols per -

144

(elegir la vocal más resonante según el registro)

Bar solo

duts a - - o - - a
/a - o o a - a/

147

Bar solo

com sen - to ro - dar

150

Bar solo

ve-lles tar - ta - nes pels ri - als de Si - ne -

Sinera : Areyns

155

Bar solo

ra Si - ne-ra Si - ne-ra Si -
/i - ε - ə : ə - ãŋs/ i - ε - ə i -

159

Bar solo

ne - ra Si - nera Si - ne - ra Si - ne - ra
εεø - ə i - eøø i - εø - ə i - ε - ø

163

Voz

(Ubykh) (tiempo para respirar)

saa swa - swa
ʃʷa ('mar') ʃʷa - ʃʷa ('Mediterraneo')

Solo se pronuncian las vocales

167

Bar solo

A - reyns A - reyns A - reyns
ɒ - a a - a a a æ

171

Bar solo

molto espressivo

A a - œ - a reyns

molto espressivo

174

178

vocales **o o u** vocales **i e a** *tr* *susurro* (*¡qué bonito!*)

Bar solo

ou - o o ei e e o a
 /õu õ oh ēī ε çh õh a

183

Bar solo

o ou ju ju ju ju ju ju ju m m ah! aou!
 ouh ouh yu yu yu yu yu yu yu m - m ãh! õõou/

187

Bar solo

a - ah a - - - - - ah

189

Bar solo

ah

Voice prints (VP) is a homage to our ancestors and the languages they used as tools to create and expand over large locations powerful civilisations. Ubi sunt? Where are our ancestors now? Have they disappeared? Those people and the locations they lived in are casted in infinite events created by our thoughts. We can hear the resonances of their voices in the roar of time. In VP the ancestors' voices are articulated by the voice of a baritone and of a violin who melt their timbre in resonances of the words uttered by a distant father: harmonics 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, and 9 of a fundamental Bb₁ tone:

How do we get to know them? We get acquainted with them by picking up out of those resonances the identifying features from which the voices of ancestors are assembled in our minds. We invite you to listen what they have to say to you and hence bring them back from an alleged Atlantis. VP includes phonemes, words and sentences sung and spoken in Scythian, Greek, Celtiberian (Luján, 2006; Rodríguez Ramos, 1997; Villar, 1995), Ubykh (Charachidze, 1989; Dumezil, 1931; Fell, 2012; Ladefoged, 2005), Albanian, Catalan, English, Galician, German, Spanish. Music is set to fragments of poems by Espriu (1946) (*Cementiri de Sinera, poems 4, 17*), Handke (1986) (*Gedicht an die Dauer*) and Llamazares (1982) (*Memoria de la nieve, poem 2*).

Text in the composition to be sung or spoken

Section 1: Questions, invocations, calls:

Qu-word: *Ubi* (Lat), *où* (Fr), *onde* (Gal), *dónde* (Sp), *wo* (Ger), *where* (Eng), *ku* (Albanian), *opoú* (Class. Gr), /ma:k¹ja/ (Ubykh)¹

- | | |
|---|--|
| (1) a. <i>¿Dónde están?</i>
(Spanish) | 'Where are they?'
(Ubykh) |
| b. <i>Ubi sunt?</i>
(Latin) | e. <i>Ku janë ata?</i>
(Albanian) |
| c. <i>On són?</i>
(Catalan) | f. /sa.ø.f ² .q ³ á.y/
what-3SA-become-PRT-Q
'What happend?' |
| d. /ma-ø-χa-na-y/
where-3PA-be.PL-PL-Q | (Ubykh) |

Section 1: Ancestors:

- | | |
|---|------------------------------------|
| (2) Celtiberian names (García Quintela, 2005) | (3) Celtic names |
| a. Eburia ² Kalueni | a. Fénus Farsaid (king of Scythia) |
| b. Apanus ³ Amboli | b. Goidel Glas |
| c. Api ⁴ | c. Sru |
| | d. Brath |
| | e. Breogan |

¹ Ubykh at UCLA: recording of speaker Tefvik Esenç made in 1986 by J. C. Catford.

² Celtic female name used in Galicia. Derived from "-ya", "eburo", a celtic word referring to the coniferous tree 'taxus baccata', 'tejo común ibérico' (texeiro, gal.). /beriya/, iberia

³ Brother of Apan. Apana is a female name derived from Api.

⁴ 'mother', 'water'. Name of Scythian goddess.

Section 2: Chant. Events of memory evoked through language

Language (Eng), Glossa (Greek), /b^hz̩a/ (Ubykh), Sprache (German), Gjuhë (Albanian).
They are chained in an event of infinite duration.

Sus voces braman en el tiempo

Susurros del viento

/h̩i i-y u o u/

/s f ʃ s ʃ s/ (Ubykh fricative consonants)

pse (Albanian: 'why?')

En mi memoria de la nieve.

Kroykhasis (Scythian)

En la espiral del bramido del tiempo. (Julio Llamazares, Memoria de la nieve)

Locations where memory dwells

- | | |
|--|--|
| (4) Section 6: Areyns ⁵ | (6) Artabrian Coast |
| a. Sinera
/si.né.rə/ | a. Arrotrebae
/ar.trəβ.æ/
'Artabria' |
| b. Areyns
/ə.réɲz/ | b. Artabri
'the artabrian people' |
| c. /ʃ ^w a/
'mar' (Ubykh) | c. Brigantis
/bri.ɣ̃än.tis/
'Brigantia' ⁷ |
| d. /ʃ ^w aʃ ^w á/
Mediterranean Sea (Ubykh) | d. Ωκεανός
okeanós
'Ocean' |
| (5) Scythia | e. Atlantis ⁸ |
| a. Kroy-khasis
'Caucasus' ⁶ | |

⁵ Sinera, anagram of Areyns de Mar.

⁶ Pliny the Elder in *Natural History* (77-79 A.D.) attributes a Scythian origin to the name Caucasus "kroy-khasis" meaning '(mountain) ice-shining with white snow'. Online Etymology Dictionary: <http://www.etymonline.com/index.php?term=Caucasus>

⁷ Name given by Breogan to the city of A Coruna.

⁸ Mythical island described in Plato's dialogues Timaeus and Critias, which allegedly became submerged into the Atlantic Ocean.

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